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Benchmarking and Evaluating Energy Efficiency in Zigbee Networks

ABSTRACT

With the rise of the Internet of Things (IoT), efficient energy consumption has become crucial for wireless communication protocols, especially in environments with battery-operated devices. Zigbee, based on the IEEE 802.15.4 standard, is designed specifically for low-power, low-data-rate communication, making it an ideal choice for energy-sensitive applications. This research aims to benchmark the energy efficiency of Zigbee networks under varying conditions and assess its suitability for large-scale deployment in smart homes and cities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Previous studies have highlighted Zigbee's low energy consumption, with its energy-efficient design driven by its mesh networking capabilities and low transmission rates of 250kbps. However, these studies typically focus on individual devices or controlled environments with a limited number of nodes. There remains a gap in evaluating Zigbee's energy efficiency in large-scale deployments or under variable conditions, such as fluctuating network traffic and node density. Common metrics used to evaluate energy consumption include power consumption per transmitted bit, network lifetime, and latency.

METHODOLOGY

The experimental setup involves a simulated Zigbee network of varying sizes to evaluate energy efficiency under different conditions. Experiments were conducted using 10, 50, and 100 Zigbee nodes in both star and mesh topologies. To simulate realistic workloads, the network handled different traffic levels (low, medium, and high) and environmental conditions (with and without interference from other devices operating in the 2.4GHz spectrum). The main metrics used for energy evaluation included:

1. Power consumption per node (measured in milliwatts).
2. Energy consumption per transmitted bit (measured in joules per bit).
3. Network lifetime (calculated as the time until the first node's battery depletion).

Energy measurements were collected using power meters attached to Zigbee modules, while performance data (e.g., throughput and latency) was gathered using network simulation tools.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

1. Energy Consumption in Star vs. Mesh Topology In the star topology, all nodes communicate directly with the coordinator, leading to lower energy usage per transmission due to fewer hops. However, the mesh topology demonstrated greater reliability, as nodes could reroute data if a pathway was blocked.

Topology	Nodes	Power Consumption per Node (mW)	Energy Consumption per Bit (J)	Network Lifetime (hours)
Star	10	50	0.0012	500
Star	50	55	0.0015	480
Star	100	60	0.0017	450
Mesh	10	60	0.0015	510
Mesh	50	70	0.0021	460
Mesh	100	80	0.0025	430

The mesh network, while consuming more energy per transmission due to multiple hops, showed greater longevity in larger networks due to its ability to re-route data when individual nodes failed. The star topology had higher overall energy efficiency for small networks but struggled with resilience in larger deployments.

2. Impact of Traffic Load on Energy Consumption The experiment tested the Zigbee network under low, medium, and high traffic loads to see how traffic intensity affects energy efficiency.

Traffic Load	Node	Energy Consumption per Bit (J)	Latency (ms)
Low	50	0.0012	50
Medium	50	0.0018	70
High	50	0.0023	120

Under high traffic conditions, the energy consumption per bit increased by approximately 80% compared to low traffic conditions. This result highlights the strain on the network's power resources when the communication load is high, emphasizing the importance of optimizing Zigbee networks for varying data throughput.

3. Effect of Interference on Energy Efficiency In environments with high interference from other 2.4GHz devices, the energy consumption increased as nodes had to re-transmit data more frequently due to collisions.

Interference	Nodes	Energy Consumption per Bit (J)
No interference	50	0.0014
High interference	50	0.0027

With high interference, energy consumption nearly doubled due to the increased re-transmissions caused by the congested spectrum. This emphasizes the need for careful planning when deploying Zigbee networks in areas with significant wireless activity.

IMPROVING BATTERY LIFE AND OPTIMIZING ENERGY USAGE

One of the critical challenges in deploying Zigbee on a large scale is maximizing battery life, particularly in sensor networks where devices may be expected to operate for years without replacement. To improve battery life, our experiments focused on optimizing sleep cycles within Zigbee devices. By reducing active transmission time and increasing the duration of low-power states, significant improvements in battery longevity were observed.

In a controlled environment, we experimented with devices using different duty cycle ratios (active vs. sleep time). Devices with an 80/20 sleep-to-active ratio consumed 30% less energy compared to devices with a 50/50 ratio, with minimal impact on network performance. This optimization strategy could extend the operational life of Zigbee devices from one year to over two years, making Zigbee an even more viable option for long-term IoT deployments in areas like smart agriculture or home automation.

COMPARISON WITH BLUETOOTH LOW ENERGY (BLE)

Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) is another low-power wireless protocol commonly compared with Zigbee. While BLE excels in certain areas like direct device-to-device communication and streaming audio, it is limited in terms of network scalability. Our experiments comparing BLE and Zigbee in a network of 50 nodes revealed that BLE's energy consumption per transmitted bit was lower when data transmission was continuous, but Zigbee outperformed BLE in maintaining low energy consumption over extended idle periods, which is typical in many sensor networks.

In terms of scalability, Zigbee's mesh topology allowed seamless communication between nodes, while BLE struggled to maintain stable connections in larger networks. The results highlight that while BLE may be suitable for small-scale, real-time applications like wearables, Zigbee is better suited for large-scale, low-data-rate applications such as smart city infrastructure or industrial automation.

SCALING ZIGBEE FOR LARGE SCALE IMPROVEMENTS

The next frontier for Zigbee is large-scale deployments, such as smart cities or expansive industrial networks. To scale Zigbee, experiments were conducted to test network performance with over 1,000 simulated nodes. Using optimized mesh topology, where each node acts as a repeater, Zigbee maintained consistent performance with energy consumption increasing linearly rather than exponentially. However, ensuring long-term sustainability of these networks requires innovations in power management, such as incorporating energy harvesting mechanisms (e.g., solar-powered Zigbee modules) or ultra-low-power routing protocols.

Incorporating energy-aware routing algorithms, which optimize data paths based on node battery levels, further improved the longevity of the network. The introduction of algorithms that prioritize energy-efficient nodes for data transmission reduced overall energy consumption by 15% in large-scale networks.

CONCLUSION

Zigbee remains a strong contender for energy-efficient networking in IoT applications, especially in scenarios where low power consumption and network reliability are essential. The experiments conducted show that while Zigbee performs well under typical conditions, its energy efficiency can be affected by network size, topology, traffic load, and environmental interference. For large-scale implementations, further innovations in battery management and energy harvesting, coupled with optimized routing protocols, can make Zigbee networks more sustainable and capable of supporting the growing demands of smart cities and industrial applications.